

AI, Blockchain, and Synthetic Biology: Catalyzing the Next Civilization

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the transformative potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Blockchain, and Synthetic Biology in shaping a new civilization. It introduces the concepts of knowledge tokens (AI), trust tokens (Blockchain), and life tokens (Synthetic Biology), emphasizing their roles in revolutionizing fields such as healthcare, finance, and sustainability. The ethical role of digital decentralization is underscored as a critical mechanism for ensuring transparency and equitable governance while addressing the risks of centralization and monopolization. The paper argues that while the synergy of these technologies could catalyze a more democratic and inclusive future, failure to decentralize may lead to concentrated power and unequal benefits

Humanity stands at the threshold of an unprecedented technological revolution driven by Artificial Intelligence (AI), Blockchain, and Synthetic Biology. While these technologies significantly impact specific sectors, their interconnectivity has the potential to unleash and catalyze a profound civilizational transformation. The positive ultimate outcome of such change hinges on urgent political and ethical deliberations to navigate the complexities it introduces.

At the heart of this technological triad are three distinct types of tokens: *knowledge tokens* (cognitive elements), *trust tokens* (cryptographic keys), and *life tokens* (genetic components). These foundational units allow each technology to operate autonomously while interacting synergistically.

A token is a "digital unit of value", representing fundamental entities carrying value depending on the context. In AI, they can grant access to information as knowledge tokens; as Friedman (2023) elucidates, "In deep learning, such as that implemented by the transformer architecture, the power lies in collecting a vast number of tokens as essential elements for training a neural network" (p. 381). In Blockchain, trust tokens can ensure the security of transactions through cryptographic methods, thereby granting access to the distributed trust embedded in blockchain systems (Rodrigues, 2021). In Synthetic Biology, every singular transformative building block of life can be conceptualized as a life token, the elementary genetic components that can define an organism's attributes. As referred to by Haveren et al. (2024), "Engineered living materials (ELMs) are an emerging class of materials with the potential for transformative impacts in sustainability across sectors (e.g., water, energy, health)" (p. 2846).

Artificial Intelligence: Expanding the Frontiers of Knowledge

Artificial Intelligence is revolutionizing the management and processing of knowledge. As Goodfellow et al. (2016) describe, "Deep learning provides a powerful framework for supervised learning. By adding more layers and more units

within a layer, a deep network can represent functions of increasing complexity” (p. 157). The rapid advancements in AI over the past decade have validated Goodfellow’s insights, particularly in demonstrating how increased computational power and larger datasets have expanded AI’s capabilities (p. 197).

Knowledge tokens are fundamental data units that empower AI to learn and make informed decisions. IBM’s Watson, for instance, leverages vast datasets as knowledge tokens to assist in healthcare, diagnosing diseases with greater accuracy and speed than traditional methods (Topol, 2019, p. 44). By analyzing medical records, research papers, and clinical trial data, Watson can recommend personalized treatment plans, thus enhancing patient outcomes and optimizing healthcare delivery (Yelne et al., 2023, p. 1).

These AI-driven tokens fuel digital systems that optimize processes across sectors, including healthcare, finance, and education. By democratizing access to knowledge, AI contributes to making information more accessible and actionable. However, political and social mechanisms are imperative to prevent the monopolization of this transformative power. Thus, equitable distribution systems are essential—and this is where Blockchain and digital decentralization become pivotal (Rodrigues, 2024).

It seems impossible to predict where the most advanced AI will emerge, but according to several authors, we are on the path toward Artificial General Intelligence (AGI). Recent advancements, such as GPT-4, have significantly accelerated progress, suggesting that AGI could be closer than anticipated. As stated by Feng et al. (2023), “the rapid development of AI has enabled its capabilities to surpass human activities in increasingly more fields, which indicates that the realization of AGI is getting closer.” (p. 2), particularly with the achievement of artificial ‘cognitive synergy’ (Goertzel, 2023, pp. 10-11). Consequently, AI may be nearing a singularity—a critical point from which virtually all future technological innovation could originate from a singular advanced AI system. Beyond this point, the economic applications of new products and services may tend to have the same exact origin: nothing less than that of the top-performing AI.

Given the immense power that stems from controlling technological innovations, if such a singular AI system becomes the primary source of new technologies, technological development could be dictated exclusively by those who benefit most from its advances. Therefore, this is not just a matter of technological progress; it is a matter of governance and ethics. The critical challenge is to ensure that the power conferred by these technologies is used fairly and equitably. It is imperative to discuss and implement policies that promote innovation while safeguarding the interests of a democratic society to ensure that everyone shares AI’s benefits (Rodrigues & Lopes, 2021). After all, what will be the consequences of failing to decentralize a sudden, uncontrollable power in advance?

Blockchain: Establishing Distributed Trust

Blockchain technology offers a means to guarantee trust, transparency, and democracy in the digital era. Trust tokens, represented by cryptographic keys, ensure that transactions and decisions remain transparent and auditable, particularly in fields such as AI and Synthetic Biology. Bitcoin, the pioneering blockchain application, facilitates secure, decentralized financial transactions without intermediaries like banks (Nakamoto, 2008). Ethereum extends this functionality by enabling smart contracts to autonomously execute agreements, enhancing Blockchain's role in digital governance (Zheng et al., 2020, p. 10).

Blockchain's capacity to facilitate digital decentralization is instrumental in preventing the monopolization of technological innovations. By providing a secure, transparent infrastructure for technological progress, Blockchain ensures that technological developments are shared ethically and equitably in many areas (Rodrigues et al., 2021; Rodrigues, 2024).

Platforms like Ethereum, described as “a decentralized platform that can execute smart contracts” (Zheng et al., 2020, p. 10), extend Blockchain's utility by automating and enforcing agreements without human intervention (Rodrigues, 2021). Blockchain technology facilitates digital decentralization, preventing power concentration and enabling the secure and ethical sharing of technological advancements (Rodrigues, 2021a; Rodrigues & Lopes, 2021).

Synthetic Biology: Editing the Code of Life

Synthetic Biology empowers researchers to edit and rewrite the genetic code that constitutes life. “Life tokens”—genetic components—are the building blocks for creating new organisms or modifying existing biological structures. One notable example is synthetic insulin: By engineering *Escherichia coli* bacteria to produce human insulin, synthetic biology revolutionized diabetes treatment, making insulin more accessible and affordable (Genentech, 2021).

This era of exciting possibilities in medicine, agriculture, and materials science raises concerns regarding unintended consequences and potential misuse. Synthetic biology addresses global challenges such as sustainable food production and developing advanced medical treatments by manipulating the essential genetic components. However, manipulating life necessitates an ethical and transparent political-economic framework.

Ethical and transparent political-economic frameworks are essential to ensure these advances benefit society while minimizing associated risks (Suleyman, 2023). Blockchain technology provides a mechanism to ensure that biotechnological developments are conducted responsibly, creating an immutable record of genetic modifications.

The Triad Synergy: Knowledge, Trust, and Life

True innovation emerges from the interconnectedness of AI, Blockchain, and Synthetic Biology. AI generates the knowledge necessary to solve complex problems since “[it] can analyze multiple channels of content and communication, generate summaries, ascertain relevant topics (to emerging problems), isolate proprietary and confidential knowledge, and present reusable insights that are immediately applicable to new situations” (Jarrahi et al., 2023, p. 89). Blockchain may ensure that these processes are transparent and secure. As Tapscott (2021) referred, “blockchains are transparent, searchable, verifiable, and trustworthy records of all economic activity in each network” (p. 25). Synthetic Biology can apply this additional trust to create ethical biotechnological solutions where “the fundamental transparency of the blockchain could enable individuals to track biospecimen use, and smart contracts could automate translation of potential health or personal benefits” (Gross et al., p. 3). Moreover, as blockchain technology is both transparent and secure, “[by using it], we are no longer forced to choose between missing out on the future benefits of scientific research and violations of privacy” (Racine, 2021, p. 35). Thus, the technological triad of AI, Blockchain, and Synthetic Biology can foster an ecosystem where knowledge, trust, and life complement each other, ensuring progress that is not only efficient but also ethical and inclusive.

With the convergence of AI, Blockchain, and Synthetic Biology, conceptualizing “life tokens” is not merely theoretical. For example, Natural Language Processing (NLP) in AI can be applied to protein sequencing in synthetic biology. Zhou et al. (2023) argue that by viewing amino acids as language tokens, researchers can employ unsupervised pre-training techniques from NLP to enhance protein representation, thus advancing biological research (p. 1).

The tokenization conceptual framework applies beyond cryptocurrencies and digital finance; it can securely store synthetic biology's foundational components. In other words, blockchain's transparency and immutability can ensure that advances in genetic engineering are conducted ethically and contribute to maintaining public trust in biotechnological applications.

However, the political ramifications of this technological revolution are profound, necessitating the adaptation of governance systems to address emerging challenges. The combination of Blockchain's decentralization (Rodrigues et al., 2021), AI's cognitive power (Goodfellow et al., 2016), and Synthetic Biology's genetic manipulation capabilities (Suleyman, 2023) has the potential to transform society into a more democratic and inclusive entity.

Integrating AI and Blockchain technologies presents significant opportunities to enhance security, transparency, and decentralized decision-making. Nevertheless, challenges related to security and scalability must be addressed through further research (Hussain & Al-Turjman, 2021), which is crucial to unlocking the full potential of this technological convergence.

Conclusion

The future of civilization is intrinsically linked to technological innovation, making it essential to advance research and political awareness regarding how AI, Blockchain, and Synthetic Biology—mediated through their respective tokens—can reshape society ethically by fairly and transparently intertwining knowledge, trust, and the very foundation of life. Further research is needed to explore the comprehensive integration of these technologies, ensuring their development is scientifically robust and socially responsible, ultimately paving the way for digital decentralization and fostering an ethical, sustainable, and democratic future where technology serves all of humanity, not just a privileged few.

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